

matter content.

Applying 135-40-50 kg NPK/ha as urea, TSP, and KCl respectively, significantly increased plant height of tall conventional varieties and hybrids.

Plant height of dwarf varieties V20B and IR58 was not significantly affected. The two rice hybrids were more susceptible to rice blast disease with 135 kg N/ha. The other entries were not

affected by blast. Yields of hybrids V41A/IR54 and V41A/Sadang were significantly lower than that of IR9575 Sel (see table). Therefore, these hybrids are not suited to upland conditions. □

Compatibility of six rice varieties with indica and japonica varieties

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Although the F_1 hybrids of indica/japonica crosses show semisterility, some rice varieties crossed with indica and japonica varieties produce fertile F_1 plants. These are known as wide compatible varieties (WCVs). We crossed CP-SLO₁₇, CP-SLO₁₉, 02428, Lunhui 422, Peiai 64, and SMR with six indica and six japonica testers.

The cultivars showed obvious differences in compatibility with indica and japonica varieties (see table). CP-SLO₁₇ and CP-SLO₁₉ were found to be WCVs. Cultivars 02428 and Lunhui 422 were more compatible with japonica than with indica varieties. Peiai 64 and SMR were more compatible with indicas, and were not designated WCVs. □

Fertility of F_1 spikelets in crosses of some rice cultivars and indica and japonica testers. HHRRC, Hunan, China, 1987.

Combination	F_1 spikelet fertility (%)	
	Mean	Range
CP-SLO ₁₇ /indica	81.2	68.5-91.3
CP-SO ₁₇ /japonica	85.4	78.4-92.0
CP-SLO ₁₉ /indica	80.0	73.3-86.5
CP-SLO ₁₉ /japonica	81.2	72.0-87.2
02428/indica	68.2	53.2-84.3
02428/japonica	84.2	78.4-92.4
Lunhui422/indica	74.2	68.5-89.4
Lunhui422/japonica	85.8	80.4-94.4
Peiai 64/indica	86.5	78.1-89.6
Peiai 64/japonica	60.3	41.2-85.3
SMR/indica	86.4	76.3-92.1
SMR/japonica	72.2	62.3-84.4
Indica/japonica	34.3	4.4-53.2

Salt tolerance of anther culture-derived rice lines

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Four dihaploid lines produced through the anther culture of IR51491 (IR4630-22-2-5-1-3/Pokkali) F_1 and IR51500 (IR5657-33-2/IR4630-22-2-5-1-3) F_1 , and their parents were evaluated for salt tolerance, using water culture technique

in the phytotron glasshouse at 29/21 °C (day/night temperature) and 70% relative humidity. Cultivars Pokkali and Nona Bokra were the tolerant checks.

IR51491 was designed to incorporate the semidwarf trait of IR4630-22-2-5-1-3 (Pelita I-1/Pokkali/IR2061-464-2/IR1820-52-2) into salt-tolerant Pokkali. IR51500 was designed to incorporate high-yielding traits into IR4630-22-2-5-1-3. The semidwarf IR4630 has compact tillering, poor

1. Relative response of anther culture lines and parents of IR51491 (IR4630-22-2-5-1-3/Pokkali) and of IR51500 (IR5657-33-2/IR4630-22-2-5-1-3) at salinity of 12 dS/m. IRRI, 1988.